

Supplemental Fig. S2-B

Suppl. Fig. S2-B (related to Fig. 2). **Detection and confirmation of duct lesion in human donor pancreas (gallery display).** (**B1-B2**) Lesion detection in pancreatic vibratome section via stereomicroscopy (enlarged in **B2**). (**B3-B5**) Confirmation of duct lesion via microtome-based H&E histology. The duct lesion in **B1** is examined via the gold-standard H&E histology (arrow from **B1** to **B3**, same microenvironment) to confirm the low-grade PanIN lesion and peri-lesional stroma. **B3** is magnified in **B4** and **B5** to specify the lesion.

Supplemental Fig. S2-C

Suppl. Fig. S2-C (related to Fig. 2). Detection and confirmation of duct lesion in human donor pancreas (gallery display). (C1-C2) Lesion detection in pancreatic vibratome section via stereomicroscopy (enlarged in C2). **(C3-C5)** Confirmation of duct lesion via microtome-based H&E histology. The duct lesion in C1 is examined via the gold-standard H&E histology (arrow from C1 to C3, same microenvironment) to confirm the low-grade PanIN lesion and peri-lesional stroma. C3 is magnified in C4 and C5 to specify the lesion.

Supplemental Fig. S2-D

Suppl. Fig. S2-D (related to Fig. 2). **Detection and confirmation of duct lesion in human donor pancreas (gallery display).** (**D1-D2**) Lesion detection in pancreatic vibratome section via stereomicroscopy (enlarged in **D2**). (**D3-D4**) Confirmation of duct lesion via microtome-based H&E histology. The duct lesion in **D1** is examined via the gold-standard H&E histology (arrow from **D1** to **D3**, same microenvironment) to confirm the low-grade PanIN lesion and peri-lesional stroma. **D3** is magnified in **D4** to specify the lesion.

Supplemental Fig. S2-E

Suppl. Fig. S2-E (related to Fig. 2). **Detection and confirmation of duct lesion in human donor pancreas (gallery display).** (E1-E2) Lesion detection in pancreatic vibratome section via stereomicroscopy (enlarged in E2). (E3-E5) Confirmation of duct lesion via microtome-based H&E histology. The duct lesion in E1 is examined via the gold-standard H&E histology (arrow from E1 to E3, same microenvironment) to confirm the low-grade PanIN lesion and peri-lesional stroma. E3 is magnified in E4 and E5 to specify the lesion.

Enlarged

Supplemental Fig. S2-F

Suppl. Fig. S2-F (related to Fig. 2). Detection and confirmation of duct lesion in human donor pancreas (gallery display). (F1-F2) Lesion detection in pancreatic vibratome section via stereomicroscopy (enlarged in F2). (F3-F5) Confirmation of duct lesion via microtome-based H&E histology. The duct lesion in F1 is examined via the gold-standard H&E histology (arrow from F1 to F3, same microenvironment) to confirm the low-grade PanIN lesion and peri-lesional stroma. F3 is magnified in F4 and F5 to specify the lesion.

Supplemental Fig. S2-G

Suppl. Fig. S2-G (related to Fig. 2). **Detection and confirmation of duct lesion in human donor pancreas (gallery display).** (**G1-G2**) Lesion detection in pancreatic vibratome section via stereomicroscopy (enlarged in **G2**). (**G3-G4**) Confirmation of duct lesion via microtome-based H&E histology. The duct lesion in **G1** is examined via the gold-standard H&E histology (arrow from **G1** to **G3**, same microenvironment) to confirm the low-grade PanIN lesion and peri-lesional stroma. **G3** is magnified in **G4** to specify the lesion.

Supplemental Fig. S2-H

Suppl. Fig. S2-H (related to Fig. 2). **Detection and confirmation of duct lesion in human donor pancreas (gallery display).** (H1-H2) Lesion detection in pancreatic vibratome section via stereomicroscopy (enlarged in H2). (H3-H5) Confirmation of duct lesion via microtome-based H&E histology. The duct lesion in H1 is examined via the gold-standard H&E histology (arrow from H1 to H3, same microenvironment) to confirm the low-grade PanIN lesion and peri-lesional stroma. H3 is magnified in H4 and H5 to specify the lesion.

Enlarged

Supplemental Fig. S2-I

Enlarged

Enlarged

Enlarged

Suppl. Fig. S2-I (related to Fig. 2). **Detection and confirmation of duct lesion in human donor pancreas (gallery display).** (I₁-I₂) Lesion detection in pancreatic vibratome section via stereomicroscopy (enlarged in I₂). (I₃-I₅) Confirmation of duct lesion via microtome-based H&E histology. The duct lesion in I₁ is examined via the gold-standard H&E histology (arrow from I₁ to I₃, same microenvironment) to confirm the low-grade PanIN lesion and peri-lesional stroma. I₃ is magnified in I₄ and I₅ to specify the lesion.

Supplemental Fig. S2-J

Suppl. Fig. S2-J (related to Fig. 2). Detection and confirmation of duct lesion in human donor pancreas (gallery display). (J1-J2) Lesion detection in pancreatic vibratome section via stereomicroscopy (enlarged in J2). **(J3-J7)** Confirmation of duct lesion via microtome-based H&E histology. The duct lesion in J1 is examined via the gold-standard H&E histology (arrow from J1 to J3, same microenvironment) to confirm the low-grade PanIN lesion and peri-lesional stroma. J3 is magnified in J4 and J7 to specify the lesion.